

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Acceptance Note for **TEBT-2025-0005**

Submission information table

Submission Title	Large Language Models for Data Extraction in Toxicology: Implications and Lessons Learned from the Clinical Evidence Domain
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0005
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	1 editor + 4 peer-reviewers
Submission Type	Comment ▾
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Recommendation	Accept ▾

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript is a commentary presenting an expert view of how large language models are being used to automate data extraction from studies included in systematic reviews and

evidence maps. The authors present a nuanced explanation of what Pretrained Language Models (PLMs) and Large Language Models (LLMs) are, how each is innately suited to different types of data abstraction tasks, and the implications of these differences for the challenge of evaluating the performance of language models.

The editor and reviewers found the article to be generally well-written and likely to be particularly helpful for readers who are not specialists in the use of so-called “artificial intelligence” for data abstraction in evidence synthesis. Comments largely concerned clarifying some of the argumentation, adding more explanation and background given the type of reader the manuscript is aimed at, and making sure the appendices and other supporting information is fully described and accessible to the reader.

The authors submitted a comprehensively revised manuscript which, in the judgement of the handling editor, addressed all of the issues raised by the reviewers. The manuscript has therefore been accepted for publication.

The authors should note one remaining minor issue with citation of internet resources and applications, which can be addressed during typesetting.

Acceptance Note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 1 round of revision, in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 1 round of peer-review.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15237277>

Remaining issues

1. Please check all the citations to software and internet resources. These should be in a full citation format of your choice (the typesetters will take care of the ultimate format, but author names, year, platform etc. should be present). For example, in Harvard a full application citation would be:

Developer (Year of release/update) Title of App (Version number) [Type of software]. Available at: URL (Accessed/Downloaded: date) Websites should also be fully-cited.